

OpenCon 2016 Ranchi

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Open Access India

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About OpenCon

The [OpenCon](#) is a conference for the next generation to learn about Open Access, Open Education, and Open Data, develop critical skills, and catalyse action towards a more open system of research and education organized by [SPARC](#), the [Right to Research Coalition](#), and [a Organizing Committee of students and early career academic professionals](#) from around the world.

OpenCon 2016 Ranchi

The [OpenCon 2016 Ranchi](#) is a satellite event of the main OpenCon 2016 which was hosted for the first time in Ranchi, Jharkhand and is the only second satellite event to be held in India this year. First being the [OpenCon 2016 Chandigarh](#) which was organized as a parallel event alongside the [Wiki Conference India](#) held at Chandigarh in August 2016. Previously OpenCon 2015 Kolkata satellite event was organized in

December 2015 at Kolkata by the [Open Access India](#) community of practice consisting of students, researchers, librarians, professors advocating for Open Access, Open Data, and Open Education in India. Approximately 2000 people have attended various satellite events around the world in the past 2014 and 2015.

The OpenCon 2016 Ranchi was hosted at Dept. of Zoology, [Ranchi University](#) was jointly organized by the Open Access India and the Dept. of Zoology, Ranchi University in partnership with OpenCon on 12 November 2016 from 10:00 am to 4:00 pm.

The Ranchi satellite event was well attended and was well appreciated as evident from the venue feedback register. For the event, 73 RSVP were registered on the OpenCon 2016 Ranchi event website out of which 50 were officially registered on the Eventbrite site. On the day of the event about 15 spot registrations were made at the desk. The attendees were students from Ranchi College under Ranchi University; research scholars from Department of Zoology, Department of Botany and Department of Physics of the Ranchi University; early career academic and research professionals and librarians from the Ranchi University and other colleges & institutes in Ranchi. The event was also attended by the people start-up groups, scientists from ICAR and CSIR institutes in and around Ranchi. Some of the members of the editorial boards of the scholarly journals also participated. Notable among them are staff from the Department of Publications, [XIIS](#).

Programme

All the discussions and deliberations at OpenCon 2016 Ranchi were about 'Openness' in Science and Scholarship and the [speakers](#) had delivered talks related to it. The event [programme](#) had sessions on the OpenCon's three focus areas - Open Access, Open Education, and Open Data. The event started with a welcome address by Dr. Abhijit Dutta address of Prof. K.P. Mishra and Sridhar Gutam about the OpenCon. It was then followed by the Chief Guest, Vice Chancellor, Prof. Ramesh Kumar Pandey had delivered his [speech](#) in which he stressed for the need of more awareness on Open Access, Open Data and Open Education and how the university and faculty get benefited from it and what policies and infrastructure has to be made available for taking forward the Open Access among the students, scholars and the faculty of the university.

The inaugural session was also attended by the Dean of Students Welfare, Ranchi University, Dr. S.C. Gupta.

After the inauguration, a session on Open Access was organized in which Sridhar Gutam presented on [Open Access to scholarly communications](#). This was followed by slides presentation on behalf of Dr. Diptanshu Das about the public peer review journal, [Wiki Journal of Medicine](#). The Open Access session was followed by an extensive session on Wikipedia under the Open Education focus area which was mainly devoted for the scholars how they can make access to knowledge possible. This session was conducted by Mr. Titu Dutta from A2K, CIS, Bangalore and Mr. Gangadhar Bhadani, Wikipedian from Ranchi. In this session, there were extensive discussions and deliberations on why scholars need to edit Wikipedia and what is notable and what is not and how to edit and contribute into Wikipedia was practically demonstrated to the attendees. During the session, a web page of the Vice Chancellor of the Ranchi University was also created. For the benefit of the faculty who had attended the event, Mr. Ravi Murugesan, associate from [INASP](#) had delivered talk via web on a perspective on [Moodle and MOOCs](#).

On Open Data, Ms. Alka Mishra and Mr. Sitansu Mahapatra's recorded [video](#) talk on Open Government Data - [Data.Gov.In](#) was presented. It was followed by the session on 'Open Access Movements in the World' in which Ms. [Jamila Jaber](#), Central Library Director, [Islamic University of Lebanon](#) had spoken about Open Access in Arab countries. And in the special session on DOAJ (Directory of Open Access Journals) which was organized to address the question about questionable publishers increasing in numbers in India and how the DOAJ trying to build a white list of quality Open Access journal's directory for the scholarship worldwide. Opening the session on DOAJ and Global South by Dominic Mitchell, spoke about the DOAJ activities and its work. This was followed by remote talks by the two Ambassadors of DOAJ in India Ms. Leena and Ms. Vrushali on [questionable publishers](#) and DOAJ application process respectively. It was followed by discussion on the Best Practices in Publishing - the DOAJ approach.

Vice Chancellor's Address at the OpenCon 2016 Ranchi (Prof. R.K. Pandey)

Distinguished faculty, Open Access India community members, attendees, students, colleagues and friends. It is my pleasure to be here at the OpenCon 2016 Ranchi satellite event which is happening here at our Ranchi University. I congratulate the faculty, particularly Dr. Abhijit Dutta, & students of the Dept. of Zoology and the Open Access India community for organizing this scholarly meeting cum workshop. I am informed that the faculties and students from other institutes and colleges in and around Ranchi had come to participate in this event. As already Dr. Sridhar Gutam, Convener, Open Access India had informed us what is OpenCon and its satellite event; I will not go into the details into it. However, I would like to make a few points here, which you may deliberate in today's sessions.

We know that Knowledge grows when it is shared unlike money! So, we should always look for ways and means to share our knowledge. The future is all about knowledge-based societies and economies. I, therefore, stress that Open Access to Research Information and Knowledge should be our way when we are academicians. The Universities produce knowledge and it should be available to everyone. How we can make it possible, we need to explore the ways and means. Many of us are aware about the Open Access journals and I hope that in today's deliberations, you would know more about why Open Access to Scholarly Research outputs and Open Access to Data is required? But, we need to be cautious on the questionable publishers and publications. You may see on the schedule, one of the speakers is going to talk about this issue. I see many articles on various portals about these questionable publishers and our country has many such journals and publishers. This is giving us a bad name among the international scholarly communities. I wish that the scholarly societies based in Ranchi and elsewhere should address this issue and work building credible scholarship.

And I see that there is also a session on Open Education. This is one area in which we also need to look at how best we can make our courseware or the faculty lectures available for the public to learn and gain knowledge. We may have to work on the infrastructure and other

modalities. The MHRD had already worked on MOOCs (Massive Open Online Courses). In December 2014, the Department of Biotechnology and Department of Science and Technology had adopted an Open Access policy which makes it mandatory to submit the research outputs produced with its funding to a public open access repository. We may also need to explore the possibility to adopt such a mandate and establish a repository for our Ranchi University, which would help us to know the landscape of the university's scholarship faculty wise and department wise across the years.

With this, I end my address here and I hope that today's event would help you all and also the management how these issues which are concerned to the researchers and faculties can be addressed and streamlined for the progress of the science and scholarship. Thank you.

Photographs

Dignitaries and Attendees at the Registration Desk

Dignitaries on the Dias (left to Right: Prof. K.P. Mishra, HoD, Zoology, Prof. R.K. Pandey, VC, Ranchi University, Dr. S.C. Gupta, DSW, Ranchi University).

Dr. Abhijit Dutta in Welcome Address

Attendees

Attendees

Prof. K.P. Mishra Addressing the Audience

Prof. R.K. Pandey, VC, Ranchi University Addressing the Audience

Prof. R.K. Pandey, VC, Ranchi University Addressing the Audience

Dignitaries on the Dias (left to Right: Prof. K.P. Mishra, HoD, Zoology, Ranchi University, Prof. R.K. Pandey, VC, Ranchi University, Dr. S.C. Gupta, DSW, Ranchi University and Dr. Abhijit Dutta, Assoc. Professor, Ranchi University)

Sridhar Gutam, Convener, Open Access India presenting on OpenCon

OpenCon 2016 Ranchi Group Photograph

Titu Dutta, A2K, CIS and Gangadhar Badani in the Open Education & Wikipedia Session

Resource Persons

- Alka Mishra <amishra@nic.in>
- Diptanshu Das <das.diptanshu@gmail.com>
- Gangadhar Bhadani <gbhadani@gmail.com>
- Jamila Jaber <jamilajaber@gmail.com>
- Leena Shah <leena@doaj.org>
- Ravi Murugesan <ravi@uwalumni.com>
- Titu Dutta <trulytito@gmail.com>
- Vrushali Dandawate <vrushali@doaj.org>
- Sridhar Gutam <gutam2000@gmail.com>

Programme Committee

- Dr. S.C. Gupta, Dean of Students Welfare, Ranchi University (Chairman)
- Prof. K.P. Mishra, Head, Department of Zoology, Ranchi University
- Dr. Abhijit Dutta, Dept. of Zoology, Ranchi University (Convener)
- Prof. Sanjoy Misra, Department of Chemistry, Ranchi University
- Dr. Uday Kumar, Department of Chemistry, Ranchi University

- Dr. B.K. Sinha, Dept. of Zoology, SS Memorial College, Ranchi University
- Dr. Sridhar Gutam, Open Access India

Participants

Sl. No.	First Name	Last Name
1	Abhijeet	Ghosh
2	Abhishek	Srivastava
3	Ajay	Srivastava
4	Akshay	Makar
5	Amit	Kumar
6	Anjali	Kumari
7	Ankush	Sharma
8	Anurag	Tripathi
9	Arshia	Naaz
10	Arundhati	Ray
11	Asish	Rout
12	Asit	Chakrabarti
13	Basanta Kumar	Das
14	Chandrathwaj	Nayak
15	Chitra	Sharma
16	Chittaranjan	Samantaray
17	Debu	Mukherjee
18	Deeksha	Deep
19	Ganesh Chandra	Baskey
20	Geetanjali	Singh
21	Hena	Kausar
22	Joe	Hill

23	Kanchan	Srivastava
24	Khushboo	Tigga
25	Kuldip	Suman
26	Kumari	Neetu
27	Kush	Keshri
28	Ladly	Rani
29	Mahesh	Bhatt
30	Manoj	Kumar
31	Namita	Singh
32	Nayeema	Khatoon
33	Neeta	Lal
34	Neetu	Kumari
35	Nilanjan	Sil
36	Nuzhat	Afroz
37	Paras	Jain
38	Pradip Kumar	Sarkar
39	Prince	Roshan
40	Rajesh Kumar	Singh
41	Rashmi	Baruah
42	Rehan	Akhtar
43	Rinku	Paul
44	Ritesh	Kumar
45	Sajalendu	Ghosh
46	Saloni	Swaroop
47	Sameer	Lakra
48	Sandeep	Rawal
49	Sanjay	Xaxa
50	Sanyukta	Kumar
51	Shaista	Parween
52	Shalini	Lal

53	Shamshun	Nehar
54	Shashank	Rai
55	Shilpa	Tiwary
56	Shiny	Kachhap
57	Shubham	Kumar
58	Soma	Karmakar
59	Sunil	Choudhary
60	Supriya	Singh
61	Tapas	Saha
62	Umesh	Shukla
63	Vikas	Kumar
64	Vivekanand	Kumar

Resources: <http://www.slideshare.net/openaccessindia/>